

SYNTHESIS OF FIVE AND SIX MEMBERED RING KETONES WITH A LONG SIDE-CHAIN FOR USE AS PERFUMES

BY S. M. GUPTA AND S. S. DESHAPANDE

Synthesis of 2-*n* heptylcyclopentanone, 2-*n*-heptylcyclohexanone, 3-methyl-5-*n*-heptylcyclopentanone, 2-geranylcyclohexanone by attachment of the long side-chain to the corresponding five or six membered ring ketone is described. Preparation of 2-hexyl-3-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenone by Frank's method is also described. When the side-chain is in position-2 the synthetic product can act as a perfume.

Jasmone (I), the odoriferous principle of jasmine blossom, was first isolated by Hesse (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2617). The assignment of its structural formula involving a five-membered ring was done independently by Treff and Werner (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1521) and by Ruzicka and Pfeiffer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, 16, 1208). Its presence in the extract of neroli and jonquil flowers was claimed by Elze (*Reichstoffindustrie*, 1926, 19, 181).

Its synthesis was achieved by Treff and Werner (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 640) and also independently by Hunsdiecker (*Ber.*, 1942, 75, 442).

The synthesis of other five or six-membered ring ketones having a long side-chain in position-2, with or without a double bond at Δ^2 and with or without a methyl group in position 3, was achieved by a number of workers (Treff and Werner, *loc. cit.*), Plattner and Pfau (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1937, 20, 1474), Hudsdiecker (*loc. cit.*), Staudinger and Ruzicka (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 245) and it was found that generally these products could act as synthetic perfumes (Werner, *Fette U. Seifen*, 1938, 45, 623).

In general, these methods consist in first preparing an open-chain molecule with one or more carbonyl groups and a long carbon chain in the desired position and then cyclising the same. The ketones described in this paper have been synthesised by us differently. *cyclo*Pentanone, *cyclo*hexanone and 3-methyl*cyclo*pentanones were treated with sodamide in benzene and by reacting the sodium compound, so formed, with terminally halogen-substituted carbon chain, the latter was attached to the ring obviously in α -position. The chain contained from six to ten carbon atoms. 2-*n*-Heptylcyclopentanone (II), 2-*n*-heptylcyclohexanone (III), 3-methyl-5-*n*-heptylcyclopentanone (IV) and 2-geranylcyclohexanone (V) have thus been prepared.

Position-5 by inference.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2-n-Heptylcyclopentanone (II).—Sodamide (5.8 g., coarse granule, B. D. H.) was added in instalment to *cyclopentanone* (12.6 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath under dry conditions till ammonia ceased to be evolved (7 hours). *n*-Heptyl bromide (27.0 g., 178°-180°) was then added and the heating continued until the mixture showed slight alkalinity (10 hours). More heptyl bromide (about 2 g.) was added and the heating continued until the mixture was neutral. The product was then poured into water, the benzene layer separated, washed, dried over calcium chloride and the solvent distilled off. On fractionating the residue, a pale yellow liquid distilled at 158°-159°/16 mm. (130°/10 mm. A. S. Pfau, U. S. P. 2069/861, 1937), yield 6.2 g. It has a faint but a pleasant odour. (Found : C, 78.5 ; H, 11.7. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{22}O$: C, 79.1 ; H, 12.1 per cent).

Its semicarbazone crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 160°. (Found : N, 17.9. $C_{13}H_{23}O N_3$ requires N, 17.5 per cent).

2-n-Heptylcyclohexanone (III) was prepared in the manner as above using sodamide (3.9 g.), *cyclohexanone* (9.8 g.) and *n*-heptyl bromide (18.0 g.). It is a pale yellow liquid with a pleasant odour and it boils at 176°-178°/18 mm., yield 5.0 g. (Found : C, 79.3 ; H, 12.5. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{34}O$: C, 79.6 ; H, 12.2 per cent).

Its semicarbazone crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 183°. (Found : N, 17.1. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{27}O N_3$: N, 16.6 per cent).

3-Methyl-5-n-heptylcyclopentanone (IV) was prepared in a similar way as above from sodamide (3.9 g.), 3-methyl*cyclopentanone* (9.8 g.) and *n*-heptyl bromide (18.0 g.), yield 4.5 g., b. p. 168°-170°/18 mm. (Found : C, 79.1 ; H, 11.6. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{24}O$: C, 79.6 ; H, 12.2 per cent).

2-Geranylcyclohexanone (V) was prepared from sodamide (15.6 g.), *cyclohexanone* (14.1 g.) and geranyl chloride (b. p. 104°-105°/10 mm., 24.8 g.). It is a pale yellow liquid with ginger like odour and distils at 164°-166°/10 mm., yield 7.1 g. (Found : C, 81.6 ; H, 11.5. $C_{18}H_{30}O$ requires C, 82.1 ; H, 11.1 per cent).

Its semicarbazone crystallises from alcohol and melts at 187°. (Found : N, 14.7. $C_{17}H_{29}ON_3$ requires N, 14.4 per cent).

2-Hexyl-3-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenone (VIII) : *Formation of Lactone*.—Grignard reagent prepared from magnesium (2.4 g.) and *n*-heptyl bromide (17.9 g.) in dry ether was gradually added to ice cold ethereal solution of ethyl levulinate (15 g.). After standing at 0° for one hour and then at room temperature for another hour, the reaction mixture was poured into cold dilute sulphuric acid. After extraction with ether, washing, drying, and removal of the solvent, the lactone obtained distilled as a pale yellow, mobile liquid at 146°-148°/12 mm., yield 4.8 g.

It has a peach like odour. Considerable amount of a high boiling liquid was left after fractionation of the lactone. (Found : C, 71.9 ; H, 11.6. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{22}O_2$: C, 72.7 ; H, 11.1 per cent).

On adding phosphorus pentoxide (2.5 g.) to the lactone (4.6 g.) in a small distilling flask and warming, the contents turned black. The mixture was distilled at a low pressure when 2.6 g. of a light yellow, mobile liquid with a strong pleasant odour, b. p. 126° - $128^{\circ}/12$ mm., (Hunsdiecker, *loc. cit.*, gives b. p. $144^{\circ}/18$ mm.) was obtained. As the amount of the ketone was too small for purification, the crude ketone was turned into its semicarbazone. The latter, crystallised from alcohol, melts at 165° (Hunsdiecker, *loc. cit.* gives m. p. 164°). (Found : N, 18.3. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{23}O N_3$ requires N, 17.7 per cent).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

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